

GLOSSARY OF INDUSTRIAL HERITAGE TERMS: METHODOLOGY IN THE CONTEXT OF SCALING WORK WITH CULTURAL LEGACY

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Abstract. *The state of the research and project discourse of specialists working with industrial heritage as part of the cultural heritage is characterized. The stages of the author's creation of a glossary of industrial heritage terms (in collaboration with E. V. Alekseeva) are presented. The choice of the main methodological approaches that provided the logic for the selection and structuring of glossary materials is justified.*

Key words: *industrial heritage, cultural heritage, glossary, work with industrial heritage, criteria for selecting terms*

Аннотация. *Охарактеризовано состояние исследовательского и проектного дискурса специалистов по работе с индустриальным наследием как частью культурного наследия. Представлены этапы создания автором глоссария терминов индустриального наследия (в соавторстве с Е. В. Алексеевой). Обоснован выбор основных методологических подходов, обеспечивших логику отбора и структурирования материалов глоссария.*

Ключевые слова: *индустриальное наследие, культурное наследие, глоссарий, работа с индустриальным наследием, критерии отбора терминов*

INTRODUCTION

Since 2019, my colleagues from the Ural Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences and me have been working to create and publish the Atlas of the Industrial Heritage of Yekaterinburg. Its necessity is due to the understanding of how quickly the unique cultural and technological past of the regional capital of the Urals is disappearing, on the one hand, and how the attitude of specialists and the public to heritage in general is changing. The Atlas is currently in print. During its writing the research group (Doctor of Historical Sciences E.V. Alekseeva, Doctor of Philosophy T.Yu. Bystrova, Doctor of Geographical Sciences V.V. Litovsky, Local historian S.A. Patrushev) came up with the idea of writing a chapter on the terms of industrial heritage, which later turned into a glossary-book (Picture 1).

The purpose of the article is to show the relevance and methodological foundations of such a research and reference text, since specialists in other types of heritage in other countries and regions definitely have similar problems that affect scientific and project work, professional and social communications, clarity of goal formulation, clarity of expert assessments state of objects and results of working with them.

We interpret industrial heritage as part of the world cultural heritage [10], the value of which became noticeable to the public and specialists much later than many other objects and artifacts. Thus, out of 1,121 UNESCO sites (2019 version), only less than fifty are related to the history of technology and production. The more important and responsible is the activity in this area, and therefore the conceptual tools of professional reflection and design of design decisions.

Picture 1. The cover of the glossary of industrial heritage terms

The global experience in working on the territories with industrial heritage, observed in regions such as the Ruhr in Germany, Monterrey in Mexico, the northern part of Great Britain, industrial cities in Poland, Spain, Brazil, Canada, China, and others, underscores the potential of heritage actualization, preservation, and development as pivotal factors in regeneration, renewal, and economic revitalization. Concurrently, the Russian context, exemplified by cities like Moscow, Kazan, Kaliningrad, etc., offers insights into broader approaches to architectural and urban heritage conservation and utilization.

This accumulated experience necessitates a meticulous examination, seeking adaptable strategies that account for each nation's distinctiveness. Furthermore, it underlines the considering settlement scales, acknowledging the impracticality of directly transferring large city heritage renewal practices to smaller urban centers. Factors such as lifestyle, mindset, and socio-economic status render such transplantations unfeasible. However, it's imperative to recognize that smaller municipalities may face terminological challenges due to a dearth of specialized professionals, potentially impeding progress and affecting project outcomes.

Brief description of the state of work with industrial heritage at the present stage

The topic of industrial heritage was actively raised about half a century ago [5]. It was first developed by specialists from the USA, Germany, and Great Britain, which led to the prevalence of English-language terms denoting various methods of working with industrial heritage, and then to their penetration and rooting in thesauri of other countries [2]. Today, the interdisciplinary nature of working with such heritage is manifested in the creation of mixed teams, where each of the participating parties uses a different vocabulary. Architects, urbanists, developers, cultural scientists, historians, museum workers and representatives of other specialties, both humanities, natural sciences and design, bring disciplinary, national and regional originality to the ideas of updating former industrial sites, buildings, and structures. This process enriches the terminological apparatus and sometimes leads away from the systematic accuracy that is required in scientific discourse. Interdisciplinarity today underpins the transition from a “point-based” to an “environmental” vision of heritage objects, which presupposes the desire to preserve and update not individual buildings or technical devices, but complexes, production chains, space, and the environment.

Accordingly, professional work with cultural heritage in cities in the 2010–2020s. assumes that we are talking not only about individual certified objects that have the appropriate status, but

about the entire complex of historical buildings – buildings of various types, from places of worship to factories, from private mansions to warehouses, shops, train stations, etc., which do not necessarily have the status of monuments [13], but which arose due to certain socio-economic processes. In different regions and cities of different sizes, not only the condition of these objects and complexes varies, but also the attitude towards them on the part of administrations, the population, entrepreneurs, and tourists. As a rule, objects are not united into any territory with a common sociocultural and urban planning function; they are discrete, used “as it happens” or not used at all; their socio-economic potential in relation to the city as a whole, strengthening its sustainability [13] is not sufficiently realized or is not noticed even by specialists. Moreover, it is these objects that constitute the core of the city and its identity, which means, with appropriate modification and rehabilitation, they can be the “points of growth” of the city, since they already acted as such once. For a realistic and complete assessment of the state of a place, a whole set of criteria is needed, developed and used today by authors from different countries [3], [6].

As authors, we sought to consider the many concepts, terms, concepts, methods applied to the heritage of the industrial era by researchers and practitioners around the world - in dissertations, monographs, articles, project documentation. At the same time, we understood that their unified system was unlikely to emerge, because the working conditions of specialists are very different, and the post-non-classical scientific paradigm allows the coexistence of many methodologies, and this increased the relevance of the glossary in our meaning. Having collected many publications and selected the main definitions, we presented in the book a palette of domestic and foreign approaches to the use of industrial heritage through links to glossary articles. In the text of the work there are also mutually opposite interpretations (for example, in the case of the so-called “re-terms” – revalorization, revitalization, rehabilitation, etc.) [5].

To select source texts and identify the most comprehensive concepts, we used the results of the previous research stage [4], when, in addition to the historical one, we were able to identify and analyze four main practical and professional discourses in working with objects and territories of industrial heritage: architectural, town planning, development, urban approaches. Their large-scale concepts, which are used to actualize industrial territories in cities (working with an industrial territory as a cultural landscape, working with architectural objects in the city, rehabilitation of industrial territories using landscape architecture, cultural regeneration, working with degrading objects, etc.), outlined the external scientific framework of the glossary.

Identification of the methodological basis of the glossary of industrial heritage terms

As stated above, the new heritage paradigm blurs the line between certified and non-certified objects, will allow partial interference in their structure, etc., especially taking into account the fact that the technical systems and objects of the past largely did not take into account the landscape and natural characteristics of the territories [8, p. 690]. Hence, among the humanitarian methods, we relied, first of all, on approaches that ensure overcoming the value vertical in working with cultural heritage, avoiding the division into “high” and “low”, “masterpieces” and “mainstream”, “pure” style and its provincial variations. This is achievable by relying on the ideas of historicism (M.S. Kagan, V.V. Alekseev, etc.); recognition of the importance of everyday culture (F. Braudel, M. Bloch, L. Le Fevre, J. Le Goff, etc.); axiological approach (F. Nietzsche, L. N. Stolovich, E. Markarjan, etc.); semiotics, the theory of “cultural landscape”. Particularly significant is the concept of “cultural landscape” (O. Schlüter, K. Sauer, H. Birks [12], etc.), largely implemented in the Ruhr region in Germany. She seeks to emphasize the interaction of natural, cultural and socio-economic principles in human habitats and explain

the nature of their connection not only by climate or economic specialization, but also by the value system and mentality of the inhabitants [8], [9]. For the tourism tasks mentioned above, the cultural landscape as a product is useful in that it has structural, functional, morphological integrity, which makes it easy to identify the territory (Yu.A. Vedenin, M. E. Kuleshova). The semiotic approach, first of all, according to Yu.M. Lotman, allows us to raise the question of the meaning of historical and architectural heritage, in particular, to develop a classification of the degrees of degradation of objects and complexes of historical and architectural heritage, taking into account the attitude of residents, investors, and tourists. The choice of the range of named humanitarian methodologies ensured the priority of concepts associated with qualitative research in the glossary.

Reflexive modernity concept played significant role in the choice of design terms of industrial heritage processes, in contrast to the postmodern doctrine, speaking of the possibility of continuing the heritage objects life in a other economic stage through its creative rethinking. Approach`s proponents talk about the continuity of modernization processes – with a qualitative difference between its two stages. The first modernity, begun in the time of the industrial revolution in the second half of the 18th century, gives birth to the “logic of the steam engine” (G. Lehmann). It is characterized by rationality, a high appreciation of scientific and technical inventions, the emergence of mass production of goods, and the deepening differentiation of different spheres of life. It is where most of the objects classified today as industrial heritage appear. The second modernity is a risk society with a high degree of instability (U. Beck), disunity, but also emancipation of individuals. It needs a meaningful overcoming of all variants of mechanistic discreteness, including through comprehension of historical connections. This concept provides an inherent justification for the revalorization of industrial heritage without connection only with external reasons such as tourism, as well as the inclusion of non-professionals (city activists, participants in participatory projects, initiators of creative clusters on the site of former industrial enterprises) in activities to update it.

The ordering of our vision of industrial heritage (in particular, in the large city) was facilitated by a systematic approach, what allows us to see the territory as a genetic and functional whole, in the unity of the interrelations of its elements and subsystems [1], [4], [11]. In line with the system methodology, we for the first time studied the evolution and heritage of the water-energy system of Yekaterinburg, its planning decisions, largely determined by the places of extraction of raw materials and the needs of factories (at the same time, subordinated to the rational logic of regular cities of the 18th century), its transport system and communications.

The selection of value-colored terms was carried out based on the ideas of revalorization of industrial heritage [2] as recognition of the value of material and cultural objects, products created in the industrial era, with the possibility of discovering new semantic and functional meanings in them. The novelty of using the theme of revalorization is associated with the focus on identifying, revealing and developing the original values of objects and territory, rather than constructing and “planting” new meanings.

As a result, we can talk about three main principles of the glossary.

- The principle of multi-paradigmality is due to the interdisciplinary nature of working with industrial (and other) heritage. At the level of definitions and comments to them, it is necessary to record all the nuances of the vision of a particular phenomenon, which will help in the future to come to more precise formulations that are understandable to representatives of different spheres.

- The principle of openness presupposes the constant updating of such an information resource as a glossary. It allows the text to remain relevant.

- The principle of systemacity is associated with a systematic understanding of the industrial heritage of any city or territory. It led to the fact that the text is divided into smaller thematic sections, which are more convenient to work with [1], [10].

CONCLUSION

A careful selection of elements of the research program ensured the representativeness of the materials: the publication includes an alphabetically arranged glossary indicating sources, a list of a number of international and Russian organizations related to the study and preservation of industrial heritage, a list of relevant international conventions and legislative acts of the Russian Federation, as well as specific decisions on objects of industrial heritage of the Urals. The glossary articles have different lengths and belong to different authors, so the reader has the opportunity to compare positions and derive their own formulations. In some cases (“factory city”, “industrial archaeology”, “industrial landscape”, etc.) 3–5 points of view are given.

In general, we understood that, due to the low degree of development of the problem, the work needed to be built at the intersection of two levels of scientific data - empirical, taken from the practices of protecting and updating industrial heritage sites in cities, and theoretical, gleaned from various sources of analytical, reference and encyclopedic, of a design nature. The experience of selecting terms for a polyphonic and, at the same time, logically coherent glossary of cultural heritage may be useful to specialists in other countries and regions.

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